

Founder’s Personal Branding as Proposed Strategy for a Cost-Efficient Marketing Strategy (A Case Study of Skin Game)

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ABSTRACT: Skin Game is an Indonesian indie beauty brand that launched on 2020. Skin Game’s sales channel focused on majority of online channels and a part of offline channels. Based on external and internal analysis, it is a matter of fact that Indonesian beauty industry keeps on rising from year to year. Indonesian consumers are interested in purchasing and using beauty products sourced from local brands. However, although the market shows a good potential, however Skin Game’s profitability keeps on dropping from year to year. In order to gather primary, qualitative research is being done such as interview with brand manager and account. Also, a focus group discussion with Skin Game consumers also being done. Moreover, to gather secondary data, books and research journals are being used. In conclusion, Skin Game’s profitability remains questionable although the beauty industry shows positive potential throughout the year. Hence, in order to survive the tight competition, Skin Game needs to re-evaluate the cause of its downturn profitability.

KEYWORDS: Beauty Products, Indie Beauty Brand, Indonesian Consumers, Local Brands, Profitability.

INTRODUCTION

The local beauty industry became very popular and saturated, whereas more local beauty brands were launched in the past years. As reported by Indonesia’s FDA, there has been an increase in the number of business actors in the beauty industry from 819 in 2021 to 913 in 2022, this is equivalent to growth of 20.6% in 2022. In addition, based on data from the National Industrial Information System (2022) Cosmetics Industry recorded as being able to absorb a workforce of 59,886 people. Moreover, quoting from the official Indonesia’s FDA website, they stated that, until the beginning of 2023 there are 1,772 Notification Owner Business Entities or around 47% of the total cosmetic distribution permit holders. If you look at the cosmetic notification data, registered cosmetics occupy 55.99% of the total Drug and Food products registered with the POM Agency, or as many as 265,723 cosmetic product items. This proves that cosmetics have become a primary need for various groups of Indonesian society. However, the larger the potential of beauty market grows aligns with the rise of new competitors in the beauty industry that cause the competition to be tighter among local beauty brands including Skin Game. The best strategy for Skin Game to implement in order to stay relevant in the growing beauty industry is still questionable.

BUSINESS ISSUES

Due to the massive amount of beauty brand launches that created a saturated market in the local beauty industry whereas this has impacted Skin Game revenue became very fluctuate. Moreover, net profit margin keeps on decreasing due to the increase of marketing and operational cost. Although other costs keep on increasing, sadly Skin Game is unable to increase its product price due to the price competition among beauty industry rivalry. Revenue was stagnant and profit keeps on decreasing from year to year became a serious problem for Skin Game.

Table 1. Skin Game’s Profit (Author, 2024)

<i>Year</i>	<i>Profit to Revenue Ratio</i>
2020	30%
2021	23%
2022	21%
2023	19%

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The author conducted a focus group discussion with participants coming from beauty consumer backgrounds. From the focus group discussion, the author found an interesting way respondents find a brand attractive to buy due to their marketing visibility. However, with limited capital and profitability left questionable, Skin Game was unable to do the same marketing activities being done by competitors. In order to increase profit, first Skin Game needs to increase revenue through brand awareness, whereas brand awareness can be increased through a series of marketing campaigns that will cost quite a lot of money and doing the wrong marketing activities will lead Skin Game to lose more of its profitability. In order to understand the root cause of decreasing profit, the author takes a closer look at the brand’s cost structure, whereas it is found that marketing costs escalate drastically from year to year. This drastic escalation was also caused by the rising competition among the local beauty industry whereas many beauty brands launched all at the same time and spent a hefty amount of marketing cost. Hence, this phenomenon caused a drastic impact on how the beauty industry runs. Skin Game’s cost structure can be seen on the table below.

Table 2. Skin Game’s Marketing Cost Distribution (Author, 2024)

	2020	2021	2022	2023
<i>Marketing Team Salary</i>	15%	15%	15%	15%
<i>Public Figure / Key Opinion Leader Partnership</i>	40%	43%	47%	56%
<i>Digital Advertisement</i>	35%	32%	28%	19%
<i>Organic Content</i>	10%	10%	10%	10%

Based on focus group discussion, key opinion leader reviews is still one of the most effective strategies that influence customers purchase. Informants are interested in purchasing a product that is being used by key opinion leaders. Key opinion leaders' cost keeps on increasing due to the increase in their rate card, for example, the key opinion leader that worked with us in 2020 gave Rp5.000.000 as an Instagram post fee. Today, one Instagram post fee is Rp15.000.000. Until today, there is no regulation on key opinion leader rate cards or fees, each key opinion leader is allowed to define any number or price that they want. The rise of key opinion leader price correlates with the rule of economy regarding supply and demand. Whereas, demand from beauty brands that are aggressively partnering with key opinion leaders keeps on increasing, meanwhile the supply is quite limited due to the difficulty of building a social media account with a lot of followers, hence not many content creators are able to build their social media account successfully.

METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection Method

Qualitative data being collected by conducting an interview and focus group discussions with participants from relevant backgrounds that able to deliver accurate information for research. Interview is being done with Skin Game’s brand manager (Imelda) and Skin Game’s accountant (Fitri). Meanwhile, focus group discussion being conducted with 7 of Skin Game’s customers.

B. Data Analysis Method

Author analyze primary data result and divided into several codes and categories. This method enables to ease the analysis process to be more accurate. The table below point out information received through primary and secondary research into several codes and categories.

Table 3. Key External Factors – Primary Data (Author, 2024)

<i>Data Collection</i>	<i>Speaker</i>	<i>Findings</i>	<i>Codes</i>	<i>Categories</i>
Interview	Imelda	TikTok suddenly being closed down by government.	Tax, Tiktok closed down	Political
Interview	Fitri	An increase of tax from 10% to 11% causing a decrease in company's profit.		
Interview	Imelda	Skin Game imported its raw materials, hence when rupiah is getting weaker is causing a higher in production cost.	Exchange rates	Economical
FGD	Thalia	Customer tend to believe and easily influenced by public figures' testimonials.	Public figure	Social
	Adinda			
	Sharen			
Interview	Imelda	Social media become very accessible to everyone from any background. Skin Game owned a private lab that encourage Skin Game to be able to do a lot of product formulations.	Ecommerce, social media, private lab	Technological
FGD	Adinda	Social media helps to promote Skin Game's products.		
Interview	Imelda	All skincare products must compliance to BPOM. All beauty brands must be registered on HAKI.	BPOM, HAKI	Legal
Interview	Imelda	There is no credible solution to solve skincare packaging waste. Skin Game owned a recycle program.	Packaging waste, recycle program	Environmental
Interview	Fitri	Skin Game use ODM partnership with manufacturer that cause difficulty to change into another manufacturer due to formulation stability and long process of regulation.	ODM	Bargaining Power of Supplier
Interview	Imelda	Beauty industry has a trend of doing big price discounts especially during payday and double date.	Price, trending brand	Bargaining Power of Buyer

FGD	Arifah	Tend to choose or purchase products from brands that are currently trending.	Trending brand	
	Sharen			
	Adinda			
Interview	Imelda	The cost of building a new beauty brand is low, hence new entrants can easily appear.	Low barrier	Threats of New Entrants
Interview	Imelda	Indonesia’s beauty market is not only filled with local beauty brands but also filled with imported skincare brands which cause more substitutes.	Imported skincare brands	Threats of Substitute
FGD, Interview	Imelda	Skin Game’s price is still competitive although competitors do a lot of discounts.	Price	Market Rivalry

Table 4. Key External Factors – Secondary Data (Author, 2024)

<i>Data Collection</i>	<i>Findings</i>	<i>Codes</i>	<i>Categories</i>
jkn.kemenkeu.go.id, 2022	PPN 11% effective date	Tax	Political
https://waskos.pom.go.id/ , 2023	55,9% of brand registered in BPOM are cosmetic brands.	Low Barrier	Market Rivalry

Table 5. Key Internal Factors – Primary Data

<i>Data Collection</i>	<i>Speaker</i>	<i>Findings</i>	<i>Codes</i>	<i>Categories</i>
Interview	Imelda	Skin Game has a structured reporting system, each division know who to report.	Organizational Resources	Tangible Resources
Interview	Imelda	Skin Game has access to our own research and development lab that ease a product research and development process.	Physical Resources	
Interview	Imelda	Patents are owned by founder.	Technological Resources	
FGD	Fitri	Although being bootstrap and has limited funding, however firm has credibility and capability of borrowing money from financial institutions.	Financial Resources	

Interview	Thalia	Michella as founder personal branding persona of the brand that is difficult to imitate.	Human Resources	Intangible Resources
	Alma			
	Putri			
Interview	Imelda	Founder owned the patents.	Innovation Resources	
Interview	Imelda	Shop reputation of 4.9/5.0 on marketplace.	Reputational Resources	
	Fitri	Relationship between Skin Game and its raw material suppliers and manufacturers.		
Interview	Fitri	Skin Game is a bootstrap company with the founder as the sole shareholder of the company's equity. All decision-making process are simple and seamless.	Firm Infrastructure	Primary Activities
Interview	Fitri	Skin Game is a team of 22 employees, the division that has the most team members is the marketing division.	Human Resource	
	Imelda	Michella is the founder of Skin Game has a strong personal branding approach.		
Interview	Imelda	Skin Game owns a research and development lab facility that enables it to speed up formulation trials and development.	Technology	
Interview	Fitri	Skin Game sourced its raw material from local and international suppliers. Some of the raw materials are imported from China, Korea and Europe.	Procurement	
Interview	Fitri	Procurement team orders raw material needed for production. Some raw materials are imported hence took longer delivery time.	Inbound	Support Activities
Interview	Fitri	Production process from raw materials is being done in a certified factory located in Jakarta.	Production	

Interview	Fitri	Finished goods are being stored at a cold storage warehouse located in Tangerang. Skin Game ensures that product quality remains stable by avoiding heat, sunlight and humid storage.	Outbound
Interview	Fitri	Skin Game advertises its product mostly on online platforms such as Instagram, TikTok and Twitter. Skin Game also enables paid marketing activities such as paid ads.	Marketing & Sales
Interview	Imelda	Skin Game dedicated a customer service team to respond to customer’s complaints and questions. Skin Game has an “easy complaint” program whereas customers receive solutions in a short period of time.	Customer Service

RESULT & DISCUSSION

A. PESTEL Analysis

i. Political

In 2023, Indonesia government reanalyzed and changed the regulation about ecommerce and social media platforms. TikTok Shop was Skin Game’s and many other beauty brand’s source of income, however the sudden change of regulation required TikTok Shop to close down and caused many beauty brands to lose their potential sales from TikTok. Gladly, TikTok Shop is allowed to be back available again however with a few new protocols. As Skin Game is a brand that heavily relies on e-commerce platforms like TikTok Shop, everytime government applies a new regulation for the e-commerce, Skin Game and other brands must follow through and has no voice or choice.

Moreover, Skin Game also suffer a great loss once government regulated tax from 10% to 11% in 2022. At that time, Skin Game was a new business, hence Skin Game suffered financially from the increase of tax.

ii. Economical

Skin Game imported most of its raw materials, hence when rupiah is getting weaker is causing a higher in production cost. Due to the exchange rate issues, Skin Game profitability suffers.

iii. Social

Since 2019-2020, the awareness of Indonesian towards the importance of skin care has increased massively. Indonesians received more and more awards in the importance of using skin care products to take care of their skin. Moreover, Indonesians easily influenced by public figure that they follow on social media, many Indonesians believe in what public figure have to say about a product.

iv. Technological

The advancement of science and technology has helped Skin Game to deliver innovative products. Skin Game owns a private lab that eases the formulation process, whereas Skin Game is able to deliver new products as soon as possible. Moreover, the advancement of technology in social media and the internet has significantly impacted the behavior of Indonesians in using the social media, many local indie beauty brands able to gain attention from customers through promoting on online platforms such as social media and ecommerce platforms.

v. Environmental

A green and sustainable company became more attractive for consumers. The same goes in the beauty industry, whereas ethical and sustainable brands caught the attention of Indonesian consumers. However, it is still remains questionable on what is the

best way to recycle and minimize skincare packaging waste. In order to contribute to environment, Skin Game owned a recycle program in collaboration with waste management parties.

vi. Legal

To protect consumers from harmful skincare products, the Indonesian government created BPOM as the watchers to ensure skincare product safety. There are a wide range of harmful ingredients being banned in Indonesia, BPOM makes sure that these harmful ingredients are not included in the skincare products marketed in Indonesia. BPOM also has the right to eliminate harmful products from the market. Every beauty product marketed in Indonesia should undergo BPOM regulations.

B. Porter's Five Forces Analysis

i. Bargaining Power of Suppliers – High

In theory, a company would be more dependent on a supplier if there were fewer vendors in the industry. In the real case scenario, there are many suppliers of cosmetic manufacturers in Indonesia. However, beauty brands cannot easily switch to other manufacturers due to ODM contracts. Moreover, the switching manufacturer process is quite uncomplicated because brands need to re-register their products in BPOM that take quite a lot of time. As a result, the supplier has more influence, has the ability to increase input costs, and can fight for further trade benefits.

ii. Bargaining Power of Buyers – Medium

Customer loyalty is low and tend to choose or purchase products from brands that are currently trending. The more visible the marketing, the more attractive for customers to purchase. Customers easily swayed away to any brands that are currently attractive in the market and products being reviewed by key opinion leaders. However, for customers with sensitive skin tend to be reluctant to switch to new product or brand due to the anxiety of using a new product that might cause irritation on their skin. Moreover, customers are price sensitive, hence discounts seem very interesting for them to purchase a product.

iii. Threats of New Entrants – Medium

The lower the barrier to enter means that more competitors may rise in the future. The lower the entry barrier means that company has less influence. In the current condition, the new barrier to entry for new entrants is very low. For entrepreneurs to own a beauty brand requires a small amount of capital, hence this became a very interesting aspect for entrepreneurs to start their venture in the beauty industry. Moreover, international beauty brands such as brands from China and K-wave heavily market their products in Indonesia. Established brands tend to have a massive and interesting marketing visibility that will gain attention from customers. From the focus group discussion conducted by the author, it is clear that brands with more visibility in social media can increase brand awareness and lead to conversion. In real life example, during the research, it is shown that Somethinc & Npure become the top of mind among respondents whereas the similarity of these two brands is the aggressive marketing campaign where both brands collaborated with brand ambassadors of famous personas.

iv. Threats of Substitute – High

The ability to raise prices and get favorable terms will be greater for businesses that manufacture items or services for which there are no direct substitutes. Customers will be able to choose not to purchase a company's goods when close substitutes are accessible, which can diminish a company's power. It depends on how expensive it would be for it to discover new markets for its goods. In the current condition, customer's switching costs to other brands is low. Hence, customers can easily switch to other brands that offer the best price deal. The greater the number of rivals and the more similar goods and services being provided by rivals, hence the less influence a company has. Local beauty industry grew massively, in order to be attractive for consumers, a good product is not enough, it is also required to acquire a massive and interesting marketing strategy. In the current status quo, through research it is found that there are 2 skincare brands that became the top of mind among respondents such as Somethinc and Npure. Both Somethinc and Npure are local beauty brands that started their venture with skin care as their first products. In the research process, it is known that these 2 brands became the top of mind due to their marketing visibility in social media, respondents answered that they need to see the brand visibility more than 3 times in order to remember the brand. However, seeing the brand visibility more than 3 times only gains awareness but not consideration to purchase. Customers are easily attracted to brands that are currently trending.

v. Market Rivalry – High

There are a total of 55,9% of brand registered in BPOM are cosmetic brands, every once in a while, there is always a new product or skincare brand launches in the market.

C. Resource Based View Analysis

Both tangible and intangible resources are used in resource-based systems; tangible resources can be further classified into three categories: financial, organizational, physical, and technical. Resources that are observable and measurable are called tangible resources.

Table 6. Tangible Resources (Author, 2024)

<i>Tangible Resources</i>	
Financial Resources	Firm’s credibility and capability of borrowing money from financial institutions
Organizational Resources	Skin Game has a structured reporting system, each division know who to report
Physical Resources	Skin Game has access to our own research and development lab that ease a product research and development process
Technological Resources	Brand and formulation trademark of Skin Game owned by the founder

Assets with a strong foundation are also known as intangible resources. Intangible resources are more challenging for rivals to evaluate and replicate since they are ingrained in distinctive regular patterns.

Table 7. Intangible Resources (Author, 2024)

<i>Intangible Resources</i>	
Human Resources	Michella as founder personal branding persona of the brand
Innovation Resources	Owned a patented ingredient
Reputational Resources	Relationship between Skin Game and its raw material suppliers and manufacturers
	Shop reputation of 4.9/5.0 on marketplace

The advantage of intangible resources over most tangible ones is that their utilization can be maximized. Intangible assets cannot be built overnight, intangible resources should be built over the years. Intangible resources are less visible and more difficult for competitors to understand, purchase, imitate, or substitute for, firms prefer to rely on them rather than on tangible resources as the foundation for their capabilities and core competencies.

Table 8. Skin Game’s Capabilities (Author, 2024)

<i>Important Capabilities Area</i>	<i>Capabilities Description</i>	<i>Conclusion</i>
Strong financial	Skin Game is a bootstrap company that has no funding from anyone, all of Skin Game’s funding came from founder’s saving.	No
Strong personal branding	Founder’s personal branding became an interesting topic for audience.	Yes
High quality machinery for production	Skin Game owned a small private lab with mediocre machinery.	No
A good customer relationship management	Skin Game able to maintain a healthy relationship with their consumers.	Yes
Accessible on online platforms	Skin Game is very active in the online platform, hence able to reach to wider audience.	Yes
Accessible on offline platforms	Skin Game’s offline platform is limited.	No

VRIO ANALYSIS

During VRIO analysis, we are able to identify what is the capabilities that is already owned by Skin Game however we are able to enhance and maximize it better. In the beginning, it is important to analyze all capabilities owned by the firm and score it through using the VRIO theory.

Table 9. VRIO (Author, 2024)

<i>Capabilities</i>	<i>Valuable</i>	<i>Rare</i>	<i>Costly to Imitate</i>	<i>Organized to Capture Value</i>	<i>Impact</i>
Strong personal branding	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sustainable Competitive Advantage
A good customer relationship management	Yes	No			Competitive Parity
Accessible on online platforms	Yes	Yes	No		Temporary Competitive Advantage

Among all resources and capability that owned by Skin Game, founder’s personal branding tends to be the most valuable. Every individual has a unique life story that is impossible to be duplicated by other individuals. Every individual has their own style and

story to tell. Moreover, founder personal branding has the cheapest marketing cost compared to many others marketing activities that has been done by Skin Game.

Table 9. VRIO Analysis of Personal Branding (Author, 2024)

<i>Valuable Capabilities</i>	Through posting video on her personal account, Skin Game’s founder able to gain awareness through soft selling contents that later on will be directed to action.
<i>Rare Capabilities</i>	Michella has a story telling skill that benefitted her personal account. Her story telling skills amaze others due to the story telling tells a lot about her life journey.
<i>Costly to Imitate Capabilities</i>	Historical: Michella has the capability of telling a story regarding the brand history and how it’s started. Social complexity: Michella has a unique approach to her audience. Audience on Michella’s personal account are very friendly and has strong attachment towards her.
<i>Organized to Capture Value</i>	There is only 1 Michella in the whole wide world, hence it is not able to be substitute.

These are the four criteria of sustainable competitive advantage, whereas founder personal branding is able to meet all four criteria.

D. Value Chain Analysis

i. Primary Activities

Firm Infrastructure: Skin Game is a bootstrap company with the founder as the sole shareholder of the company’s equity. By having this kind of infrastructure has an advantage of smooth, fast and prompt decision-making process, especially in the fast-moving beauty industry, it is necessary to create a quick decision in order to be able to follow the trends. However, the down side of this infrastructure is having limited budget and capital for the company to be able to expand and grow quickly.

Human Resources: Currently, Skin Game is a team of 22 employees that’s divided into managerial, supervisor and staff level. The division that has the most team members is the marketing division. Founder’s personal branding is one of Skin Game’s superiority. Not every brand founder has activated personal branding strategy and not every brand founder has an interesting storytelling skill. Hence, Skin Game’s founder personal branding strategy became one of Skin Game’s human resource privilege.

Technology: Skin Game owns a research and development lab facility that enables it to speed up formulation trials and development. Skin Game able to tap in the market trend and create product formulation based on the latest trend in beauty industry.

Procurement: Skin Game sourced its raw material from local and international suppliers. Some of the raw materials are imported from China, Korea and Europe. The downside of this is due to fluctuation of exchange rate.

ii. Support Activities

Inbound: Procurement team orders raw material needed for production. Some raw materials are imported hence took longer delivery time.

Production: Production process from raw materials is being done in a certified factory located in Jakarta.

Outbound: Finished goods are being stored at a cold storage warehouse located in Tangerang. Skin Game ensures that product quality remains stable by avoiding heat, sunlight and humid storage.

Marketing: Skin Game advertises its product mostly on online platforms such as Instagram, TikTok and Twitter. Skin Game also enables paid marketing activities such as paid ads.

Customer Service: Skin Game dedicated a customer service team to respond to customer’s complaints and questions. Skin Game has an “easy complaint” program whereas customers receive solutions in a short period of time. Skin Game also created a program called “complain to founder” where consumers can easily reach out to the founder.

BUSINESS SOLUTION

The differentiation strategy that Skin Game’s can offer is based on founder’s personal branding and unique positioning as basic skincare expert. Founder’s personal branding is a differentiation that cannot be replicate by anyone or anything. Nevertheless, other brands are able to use the same personal branding strategy, however it is impossible to create a persona the same exact with Michella as Skin Game’s founder. Result shows a satisfying number, whereas founder’s personal branding strategy is aligned with the main objective of seeking an efficient yet low cost strategy. Founder’s personal branding strategy does not only show positive results on the awareness stage; however, it is also successfully impacted customer’s action which cause an increase of revenue with a good profit margin.

Table 10. Key Opinion Leader Partnership Result (Author, 2024)

<i>Key Leader</i>	<i>Opinion</i>	<i>Followers</i>	<i>Niche</i>	<i>Partnership Cost</i>	<i>Revenue from Partnership</i>	<i>Return on Marketing Investment (Revenue / Investment)</i>
KOL 1		1 M	Beauty	Rp10.000.000	Rp1.390.000	-0,139
KOL 2		230 K	Beauty	Rp6.000.000	Rp104.200	-0,017
KOL 3		2,9 M	Beauty	Rp13.500.000	0	0

Result shows that key opinion leader is the most significant marketing activity that able to influence consumer purchase. However, the cost of partnership with key opinion leaders are tend to be very high and low return on marketing investment.

In fact, personal branding is way more cost-efficient compared to other marketing activities that has been done by Skin Game. Moreover, personal branding activity also brings the highest return on marketing investment compared to key opinion leader endorsements. Table below explains the cost differences between personal branding and key opinion leader endorsements. Every month, Skin Game spare a minimum budget of Rp50.000.000 to fund key opinion leader partnership. To understand better, below is the summary of Skin Game’s best performing key opinion leader partnerships.

Table 11. Skin Game’s Founder Content Result (Author, 2024)

<i>Skin Game’s Founder Username</i>	<i>Followers</i>	<i>Niche</i>	<i>Partnership Cost</i>	<i>Revenue from Partnership</i>	<i>Return on Marketing Investment (Revenue / Investment)</i>
Sajangmich	34.1 K	Beauty	Rp1.350.000	Rp6.840.000	5,066x

In conclusion, the return on marketing investment is bigger and more profitable compared to the cost incurred from key opinion leader partnerships. Hence, founder’s personal branding can be a cost-efficient strategy being applied by Skin Game.

CONCLUSION

Profit issue is a crucial issue for firm, profit allows firm to have a healthy cash flow to expand. There are times where revenue increase however profit tends to suffer. After research, it was found that Skin Game’s profit issue caused by the increasing marketing cost. Whereas, the increase of marketing cost was encouraged by the competitive nature of beauty industries, hence most beauty

brands are willing to spend a hefty amount of marketing money in order to survive and stay existent in the beauty industry. However, this action impacted Skin Game's finances that cause Skin Game's profit to suffer. Skin Game has limited marketing cost due to its bootstrapping nature whereas all capital is sourced from founder's saving, there is a very tight budget that disable Skin Game to compete with other beauty brands. Meanwhile, many of Skin Game's top competitors are being backed by investors and venture capitalist. Moreover, author also did a secondary data research towards other beauty brands that is not backed by investors, whereas they all succeeded enabling founder's personal branding strategy that allows them to have minimum marketing budget, however with a maximum impact that leads to revenue. In conclusion, Skin Game should also implement founder's personal branding strategy that will help boosting Skin Game's attention and awareness in the market. It is also known that the higher the total number of founder's followers is aligned with total number of brand's followers on social media. Whereas, total number of organic followers can be a supposition of awareness. Skin Game's inability to adapt will cause the firm's profitability to suffer. By implementing the personal branding strategy towards Skin Game's founder, it has been proven that it has successfully tested the hypothesis that founder's contents are able to gain audience's awareness and attention that will eventually leads to their action to purchase Skin Game's products. Personal branding strategy also aligns with author's external and internal analysis towards Skin Game, whereas personal branding strategy is aligned and checked all of the VRIO criteria.

RECOMMENDATION

Implementing personal branding strategy should be consistent and relevant to the brand guideline. There are many types of founder's personal branding persona, however not all persona is suitable to the brand. Skin Game is known for its trusted, science backed and educative skin care brand. Hence, founder's persona should also capture an educative, smart and elegant person. In the midst of founder's bustle in handling the business, sometimes it is difficult for founder to be able to stay consistent in creating content and making time to brainstorm the content ideas. It is advisable and recommended for founder to have a dedicated team that will help founder to develop personal branding contents. All strategy is only as good as the implementation, no matter how good a strategy is however with no implementation, it will all comes to a waste. Moreover, not every video will be productive, there are also videos that does not generate any revenue; however, it is crucial to stay consistent in video production. In addition, although founder's personal branding strategy is considered effective and cost efficient, however many founders have a difficulty in dividing their time between working on internal business process while producing contents, time management can be tricky and most of the time will be very exhausting for solo founder of an indie brand that has a limited amount of team members that can help them.

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